

WaterSafe: A Water Network Benchmark for Fault Diagnosis Research

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Abstract: Currently, in the water distribution systems literature, fault detection methods are typically evaluated on benchmark water networks that do not include real-time experimental data, or on private commercial datasets, which prohibit the reproducibility of the results. Moreover, realistic modeling of faults on hydraulic system components, sensors and actuators is often unavailable. In this work, we provide a framework for the application of fault-diagnosis methodologies on WaterSafe, a water network benchmark for fault diagnosis. The WaterSafe benchmark is a small scale replica of a water transport network constructed using industrial components and devices, while the communications are implemented in a way that resemble a water utility’s Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition system. A general problem formulation for fault-diagnosis on water systems is provided, in accordance to the mathematical model of the benchmark. Moreover, we provide a calibrated simulation model including system, sensor and actuator faults, based on observations from the real system. Finally, we provide open access to the datasets generated from the experiments containing the aforementioned faults.

Keywords: Water distribution system; networks; testbed; fault diagnosis

1. INTRODUCTION

Water Distribution Networks (WDN) are critical infrastructure systems which are crucial for the population well-being and health. These systems are prone to various types of faults, including leakages from pipe bursts (hydraulic/process faults) and malfunctions of pumps and valves (actuator faults). Water utilities are integrating ICT infrastructure in WDN as a way to mitigate these problems using smart technologies. The use of ICT brings new faults such as sensor and communication faults, and may provide pathways for malicious attackers to interfere with the system operation, through cyber-attacks.

In the WDN scientific literature, researchers have developed methodologies to detect hydraulic faults, with many of the studies focusing on leakage detection (Vrachimis et al., 2021). Globally, physical water losses are estimated between 12-20% of the total water supplied by the utilities (Kingdom et al., 2006). The developed methodologies are typically demonstrated on network models, and, less frequently, using data from actual systems. Real datasets from actual water systems are typically limited, due to the small number of sensors installed compared to the system

states. Moreover, data from these systems may be sensitive or confidential and cannot be easily shared.

In the fault-diagnosis literature, researchers have developed methodologies to detect process (Blanke et al., 2006), actuator Zhang et al. (2021) and sensor faults (Reppa et al., 2016) in various types of systems (Isermann, 2006), while methodologies have also been developed to distinguish between different type of faults. Typically the proposed methodologies are applied on benchmarks, such as the “three-tank system model” which was introduced mathematically by Wünnenberg (1990), and was later commercialized as a physical testbed by the company Amira through the “Three-Tank System DTS200”. The three-tank system is still widely used, while similar benchmarks are being created and used (Farias et al., 2018). The advantage of laboratory scale physical benchmarks is having an accurate mathematical and simulation model of a fully observable system. Actual experiments can be performed in a controlled environment, where safety of the system is not critical and various faults can be implemented.

Other open benchmarks of more advanced laboratory setups for fault-diagnosis research have been created since the three-tank system. The researchers in Syfert et al. (2003) have created and presented a benchmark for actuator fault-diagnosis based on sugar factory actuators, which was widely used by the fault-diagnosis community. The

^{*} This work has been partially supported by the European Union Horizon 2020 program under Grant Agreement No. 739551 (KIOS CoE), and by the European Research Council (ERC) under the ERC Synergy Grant ‘Water-Futures’ (Grant agreement No. 951424).

Fig. 1. (a) The KIOS Water Systems Testbed; (b) Simplified illustration of the series configuration.

Water Distribution (WADI) Testbed, described in Ahmed et al. (2017), is a research infrastructure, based on the operation of a water distribution system, oriented towards the design of safe and secure cyber-physical systems. The researchers in Jensen et al. (2018), have used a laboratory setup capable of emulating a small scale water supply system to test their methodology for pressure control in pipe networks.

In this paper, we present a new industrial control system benchmark specifically for WDN fault diagnosis research, referred to as the WaterSafe benchmark. The WaterSafe benchmark is based on the “KIOS Water Systems Testbed” (Fig. 1a), which has been developed at the KIOS Research and Innovation Center of Excellence at the University of Cyprus, to support the advancement of smart water networks research. It is designed to mimic the structure and operation of a real water transport network, with the physical size and operation times of the testbed being down-scaled versions of a real water system.

The main contribution of this paper is providing a framework for the experimental application and comparison of fault diagnosis methodologies by:

- designing a mathematical model of the WaterSafe benchmark;
- calibrating the provided model using real-data;
- computing realistic fault models of system components based on real experiments; and
- releasing an open simulation model of the WaterSafe benchmark in MATLAB/Simulink.

This paper is structured as follows: In Section 2, a physical description of the benchmark is provided. Section 3 offers the general framework in which this benchmark can be used and in Section 4 the mathematical model of the benchmark is provided. In Section 5, the identification procedure for unknown system and fault functions is provided. The system model is also given as a MATLAB/Simulink simulation model in Section 6, while all the data used and the MATLAB/Simulink model created are openly available through the links provided in Section 7. Finally the future direction of this benchmark is described.

2. PHYSICAL DESCRIPTION OF THE TESTBED

The “KIOS Water Systems Testbed”, depicted in Fig. 1a, consists of a reservoir and four cylindrical tanks connected by pipes, which allow the water flow between the tanks T_i , $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$. The reservoir operates both as the main

Fig. 2. Overview of a water network control system, equipped with an FDI module.

(infinite) water source for the main pumping station, as well as a sink for all the consumption points. The tanks serve as the supply for four urban regions, characterized by different consumer water demand patterns. The consumption patterns are generated using valves that regulate the tank outflows, located at the bottom of each tank. In each region, the storage tanks are located at a sufficiently high point, so the water is provided to the consumers via gravity. Centrifugal pumps provide to necessary energy to move water from the reservoir to the tanks, as well as between the tanks. The testbed is re-configurable so that a number of different setups for the distribution system can be realized (e.g., tanks in a row or in parallel)

The testbed consists of three elevation levels, as seen in Fig. 1a. There are two different types of cylindrical tanks; tank T1 and T2 have 50 cm height, whereas T3 and T4 have 40 cm height. For safety reasons, the operational capacity of tanks is set at approximately 35 cm and 25 cm for each set of tanks respectively. All valves operate between 0% to 100%, indicating the valve being completely closed and open respectively. All pipes of the system have flow control electronic valves, as well as manual valves. Flow and pressure at the end-points of all pipes are measured. Each tank has a level sensor installed for measuring the water level inside the tank. The overall system has a total of thirty-three sensors. Measurements are all received by a Programmable Logic Controller (PLC). The PLC provides the control signals, monitors the safety bounds and also communicates the data to an IoT Platform which is linked with MATLAB for collecting and processing the experimental data.

3. PROBLEM FORMULATION

The typical structure of a water network control system, equipped with a Fault Detection and Identification (FDI) module, is given in Fig. 2. This comprises of a physical layer with the following parts: block \mathcal{P} represents the plant comprised of actuator subsystems and the water tank network subsystems; block \mathcal{A} represents the actuators; block \mathcal{S} represents the sensors monitoring the plant. The software layer comprise of block \mathcal{C} which is the Controller module and the \mathcal{FDI} module, which is the Fault Detection and Isolation module.

In Fig. 2, for n_t water tanks, n_s sensors and n_m actuators, $x(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the state vector of the system \mathcal{P} with $n = n_t + n_m$ dynamic states, $d(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_t}$ are the disturbances

affecting the system P , $y(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_s}$ is the measurement vector, (for n_s sensors), $v(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_m}$ is the control input vector generated by the controller C (for m actuators), $u(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_m}$ is the actual control vector which may include an additive actuator fault, and $r(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the control reference vector. Controller C aims to regulate the states in accordance to the desired reference signal $r(t)$.

In water systems, faults can occur on the pump/valve actuators, the sensors and in the components of the plant itself. The faults are indicated by $\xi^a \in \mathbb{R}^{n_m}$, $\xi^s \in \mathbb{R}^{n_s}$ and $\xi^p \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and represent the actuator, sensor and system faults respectively. We consider that the aforementioned faults are additive, with process and sensor faults being state dependent. The dynamics of the physical system, described in Fig. 2, are then given by

$$\Sigma : \begin{cases} \dot{x}(t) = f(x(t), u(t), d(t)) + \xi^p(t, x); \\ u(t) = v(t) + \xi^a(t, v); \\ y(t) = h(x(t)) + \xi^s(t, x). \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $f : \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^{n_m} \times \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ represents the plant dynamics, and $h : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n_s}$ represents the dynamics of the sensors. The physical system (the plant \mathcal{P} , actuators \mathcal{A} and the sensors \mathcal{S}) is jointly denoted by Σ .

Individual faults are represented by ξ_i^j , where the superscript $j \in \{p, s, a\}$ corresponds to the type of fault (process, sensor, actuator), and the subscript i corresponds to the location of the component associated with the fault (e.g., the i -th sensor). In this work we consider the types of faults ξ_i^j (Reppa et al., 2016), can be modelled by the function

$$\xi_i^j(t, z) = \sum_{\nu=1}^{\nu^*} \beta_{\nu}(t_{2\nu-1}, t_{2\nu}) \phi_{\nu}(t - t_{2\nu-1}, z), \quad (2)$$

where β_{ν} represents the fault time profile, ϕ_{ν} is the fault function which depends on the state/input z and ν^* is the number of time intervals when the fault is present. The time profile β_{ν} can be represented as

$$\beta_{\nu}(t_1, t_2) = \beta_{\nu 1}(t - t_1) - \beta_{\nu 2}(t - t_2), \quad (3)$$

where $\beta_{\nu 1}$ is the evolution mode of the fault occurrence at t_1 and $\beta_{\nu 2}$ is the evolution mode of the disappearance at t_2 . In general, the evolution mode $\beta_{\nu k}$, $k = 1, 2$, can be modeled as

$$\beta_{\nu k}(t) = \begin{cases} 0, & t < 0 \\ 1 - e^{-\kappa_{\nu k} t}, & t \geq 0 \end{cases}, \quad (4)$$

where $\kappa_{\nu k} > 0$ is the fault evolution rate. Note that when $\kappa_{\nu k} \rightarrow \infty$, the fault can be considered as abrupt.

The aim of Fault Diagnosis and Identification FDI module, is to detect and isolate faults, given the system measurements $y(t)$ and the control signal $v(t)$ (Blanke et al., 2006), as shown in Fig. 2. The output of this module is a set $\mathcal{A} = \{a_1, a_2, \dots\}$, which is updated by adding a new alert when an alert is generated by the FDI module, i.e., when a fault is detected and/or isolated. The i -th alert a_i is a tuple composed of information related to fault detection (e.g., fault start time t_1 and fault end time t_2), fault isolation (e.g., fault type and location), and fault identification (i.e., estimation of the function $\xi_i^j(t)$ describing the fault dynamics and magnitude.

4. MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF THE SYSTEM

In this section, we introduce the modelling aspects of the testbed, as they are considered in the WaterSafe benchmark. The quantities of interest are the water flows q and tank levels h . The model of individual components is first described. The individual components affecting hydraulic dynamics are the Reservoir, Tanks and Actuator subsystems. Moreover, hydraulic dynamics are affected by process, actuator and sensor faults. The component models are combined to provide the hydraulic model of the ‘‘tanks-in-series’’ testbed configuration, illustrated in Fig. 1b. The following modeling assumptions are made during the modeling process: 1) The fluid flowing through the valves is ideal and the Bernoulli and mass continuity equations can be applied; 2) Sensors (flow, pressure, level) do not have an effect on the hydraulics.

4.1 Reservoir and Tank dynamics

The Reservoir serves as the main source of water in the testbed, as well as the sink of all outflows/demands. The quantity of interest when modeling hydraulics is the reservoir level $h_0(t)$. We assume that the minimum level of the Reservoir is h_0^{\min} , and occurs when the level of all tanks T_i is at their maximum and all pipes are filled with water. The reservoir level can be approximated by a constant, by assuming that the base area of the reservoir base is much larger than the base area of the tanks in the system, $A_i \ll A_r$, as follows: $h_0(t) \approx h_0^{\min}$.

The dynamic equation for the water level in a single tank T_i is obtained by considering the change of water level h_i . Each tank has an open flow pipe at the top which brings water into the tank and two outflow pipes at the bottom, one for water consumption and one connection to the rest of the network. The dynamics of the tank water level can be described as follows:

$$\frac{dh_i(t)}{dt} = \frac{1}{A_i} [q_i(t) - q_{i+1}(t) - d_i(t)] + \xi_i^p(t, h_i; \theta_i^p), \quad (5)$$

where h_i is the tank water level, A_i is the tank base area, q_i is the inflow rate, q_{i+1} is the outflow rate, d_i is the water consumption, and $\xi_i^p(t, h_i; \theta_i^p)$ is a process fault corresponding to a leakage on the tank. The function describing the fault and fault parameter θ_i^p is identified using experimental data in Section 5.

The water consumption $d_i(t)$ is typically considered as uncontrolled disturbance. This can be modelled using Bernoulli’s flow equation for incompressible fluids; the outflow rate from the orifice at the bottom of each tank is given by:

$$d_i(t) = \gamma_i(t) \sqrt{2gh_i(t)}, \quad (6)$$

where g is the gravitational constant and γ_i denotes the cross section area opening of the consumption outflow pipe at tank T_i . The cross-section opening is controlled by defining the settings of the consumption valve. The opening is time-varying as it represents the changing water demand. In reality, the consumption valve on the testbed is fully controllable and the variable $\gamma_i(t)$ is programmed such that $d_i(t)$ emulates demand patterns observed in real WDN. However, in practice the valve opening is not known and, sometimes, neither is the consumption in a WDN area, which this consumption outflow emulates. In this

Fig. 3. Schematic of an actuator subsystem.

work, the valve opening γ_i is considered an unknown disturbance to the system, and exhibits periodic behavior.

4.2 Actuator subsystem dynamics

The actuator subsystem is the mechanism responsible for transferring water from a tank or reservoir to another tank. An illustration of an actuator subsystem is depicted in Fig. 3. The i -th actuator subsystem consists of a Pump P_i , a pressure sensor, Local Feedback Controller (LFC), an actuator valve V_i and piping connecting the pump and valve to tank T_i . The input of this subsystem is the valve set-point $v_i(t) \in [0, 1]$, given by the controller which is encoded in the PLC. The output of the subsystem is the flow $q_i(t)$ which is the inflow to tank T_i .

In general, the response of the subsystem can be described by

$$\frac{dq_i(t)}{dt} = f_A(q_i(t), u_i(t)), \quad (7)$$

where $f_A(\cdot)$ is a function describing the actuator subsystem dynamics, while

$$u_i = v_i + \xi_i^a(t, v_i; \theta_i^a) \quad (8)$$

is the modified control input due to an actuator fault described by $\xi_i^a(t, v_i; \theta_i^a)$ with a parameter θ_i^a . The function $f_A(\cdot)$ is identified using experimental data, a procedure described in Section 5. It is assumed that the dynamics of all actuator subsystems in the testbed are identical, considering that the same equipment was used.

4.3 State-space model — Series configuration

The state-space equations describing the series configuration of the testbed (Fig. 1b) are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{h}_1(t) &= \frac{1}{A_1} [q_1(t) - q_2(t) - d_1(t)] + \xi_1^p(t, h_1(t); \theta_1^p), \\ \dot{h}_2(t) &= \frac{1}{A_2} [q_2(t) - q_3(t) - d_2(t)] + \xi_2^p(t, h_2(t); \theta_2^p), \\ \dot{h}_3(t) &= \frac{1}{A_3} [q_3(t) - q_4(t) - d_3(t)] + \xi_3^p(t, h_3(t); \theta_3^p), \\ \dot{h}_4(t) &= \frac{1}{A_4} [q_4(t) - d_4(t)] + \xi_4^p(t, h_4(t); \theta_4^p), \\ \dot{q}_1(t) &= f_A(q_1(t), u_1(t)), \quad \dot{q}_2(t) = f_A(q_2(t), u_2(t)), \\ \dot{q}_3(t) &= f_A(q_3(t), u_3(t)), \quad \dot{q}_4(t) = f_A(q_4(t), u_4(t)). \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Fig. 4. (a) The flow rate and pressure for different valve settings in an actuator subsystem; (b) Experimental data from an actuator fault occurring on the valve of the actuator subsystem of pump P_1 ; (c) Experimental data from a leak, with a hole area of 0.8cm , occurring at Tank T_1 ; (d) Experimental data from a level sensor fault of tank T_i .

The state vector x of the system and the control input vector u , when $n_t = 4$, $n_m = 4$ and $n = 8$, are defined as follows (time notation omitted for simplicity):

$$\begin{aligned} x &= [h_1, h_2, h_3, h_4, q_1, q_2, q_3, q_4]^\top, \\ u &= [u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4]^\top. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

The measured outputs are given by

$$y(t) = h(x(t)) + \xi^s(t) = Cx(t) + \xi^s(t, x), \quad (11)$$

where $C \in \mathbb{R}^{n_s \times n}$ is such that any combination of the tank water level states x_1, \dots, x_4 and the flow states x_5, \dots, x_8 can be directly measured, while $\xi^s(t, x)$ describes the sensor fault functions.

5. MODEL IDENTIFICATION AND CALIBRATION

In this section we use experimental data from various operating scenarios of the KIOS Water Systems Testbed to identify and calibrate the mathematical model used in the WaterSafe benchmark. Four different experimental scenarios were designed and executed: 1) a fault-free scenario, where step inputs are applied to identify the dynamics of the actuator subsystems, 2) a scenario which includes a leakage (i.e., a process fault), 3) a scenario which includes a valve malfunction (i.e., an actuator fault), and 4) a scenario with an electrical malfunction causing a sensor fault.

All the experiments had a run time of 7 minutes. Initial conditions (initial tank levels) vary at each experiment. At the current configuration of the testbed, a decentralized closed-loop “bang-bang” controller is encoded in the PLC, to enforce safety limits to the water level of each tank. The following rules are used for each subsystem i :

$$\begin{aligned} \text{IF } y_i(t) \geq R^u \text{ THEN } v_i &= 0, \\ \text{IF } y_i(t) \leq R^l \text{ THEN } v_i &= r_i, \end{aligned}$$

where $y_i(t)$ is the water level measurement of Tank T_i , R^l and R^u are the lower and upper tank level thresholds respectively, and $r_i \in [0, 1]$ is a predefined set-point for the valve V_i of the i -th actuator system. The reference lower bound for each tank water level is set to $R^l = 10cm$ and the upper bound to $R^u = 28cm$. The valve settings provided by the controller when $y_i(t) \leq R^l$ are set to $v_1 = 70\%$, $v_2 = 45\%$, $v_3 = 40\%$ and $v_4 = 35\%$.

5.1 Scenario 1: Actuator subsystem identification

In the fault-free scenario, step inputs are provided to the actuator subsystem of pump P_1 to identify the function describing its response. The actuator subsystem dynamics, when in fault-free operation, are identified using the experimental data and the MATLAB[®] Systems Identification Toolbox.

Figure 4a illustrates the experimental results. In the figure, the flow $q_1(t)$ (the output) of Actuator subsystem containing pump P_1 is plotted with the valve setpoint (the input) $v_1(t)$ to identify the function that relates them. In the same figure, the pressure measured at the output of the pump is also plotted. The pressure there is of interest because by observing the pressure change we can deduce when the pump is operating. The change in the state of the pump is regulated by the Local Feedback Controller (LFC), which is integrated in the pump.

There are two modes of operation, which correspond to whether the pump is ‘ON’ or ‘OFF’. When the Pump is ‘ON’, the response of the actuator system can be approximated by a first order differential equation:

$$\dot{q}_i(t) = \lambda_i u_i(t) - \alpha_i q_i(t),$$

where $\alpha_i, \lambda_i \in \mathbb{R}^+$ are constants identified using the experimental data of Fig. 4a. When the Pump is ‘OFF’, the flow is calculated using the Hazen-Williams formula to find the head-loss across hydraulic elements of a network. The LFC of each pump P_i , uses the measured pressure p_i at the outlet of the pump to decide when the pump should change mode. The pump is turned on when $p_i < p^l$ and turns ‘OFF’ when $p_i > p^u$, where $p^l = 16m$ and $p^u = 28m$ are the pre-defined lower and upper pressure thresholds for the testbed. A simplified representation of the actuator system response can be used by considering that the pressure typically drops when the pump is ‘OFF’, resulting in the gradual decrease of the flow. Thus, the flow dynamics when the pump is ‘OFF’ can be approximated, using the constant η_i , as follows:

$$\dot{q}_i(t) = -\eta_i q_i(t).$$

The operational mode of a pump can be defined by assuming that it depends only on the valve setting u_i . From Fig. 4a, it can be observed that the pump closes when $u_i = 20\%$, while the flow drops to zero only when $u_i = 10\%$. It was observed that the pump was working intermittently when $u_i = 20\%$, without allowing the flow to drop to zero. Thus, we assume for simplicity that the pump is ‘OFF’ only when $u_i \leq 10\%$. The function $f_A(\cdot)$ of (7) is then given by:

$$f_A(q_i(t), u_i(t)) = \begin{cases} \lambda_i u_i(t) - \alpha_i q_i(t), & 0.1 \leq u_i(t) \leq 1 \\ -\eta_i q_i(t), & 0 \leq u_i(t) \leq 0.1 \end{cases}. \quad (12)$$

5.2 Scenario 2: Process faults

Process faults in the testbed correspond to leakages occurring at the water tanks. Leakages are modeled as an additional consumption at each tank.

In this scenario, a fault is induced on tank T_1 , while allowing the tank to empty, to model the dependence of the leak flow on the tank level state. Fig. 4c illustrates the process fault signal $\xi_1^p(t, h_1; \theta_1^p)$, corresponding to leakage flow, and the tank state $h_1(t)$ for the experiment duration. In the figure, we can see that the tank level drops from $20cm$ down to $7cm$, for a run time of $T = 7min$. The leakage flow (from the tank) is also measured for the purpose of this experiment and it starts at $t_1 = 3.6$ minutes. The leak hole opening is known, as it is set by an electronic valve, and is equal to $\theta_1^p = 0.8cm$.

Using the experimental data, the leakage function can be described by:

$$\xi_i^p(t, h_i; \theta_i^p) = \beta_\nu(t_1, t_2) \left[\theta_i^p \left(-\frac{1}{A_i} \sqrt{2g} \right) h_i(t)^{0.5} \right], \quad (13)$$

where θ_i^p corresponds to the leak hole opening, $\beta_\nu(t_1, t_2)$ is the fault time profile corresponding to a unit rectangular pulse starting at $t_1 = 3.6$ minutes and ending at the end of the simulation $t_2 = 7$ minutes.

5.3 Scenario 3: Actuators faults

Actuators are the devices responsible for regulating the flow rate supply to the each tank. In the actuator subsystem of Fig. 3, a malfunction of the valve V_i may lead to a modified behavior. The malfunction could be a result of a pipe clogging, or a mechanical fault of the valve.

In this scenario, a manual valve between the pump and valve V_i is partially closed, simulating a clogging of the actuator subsystem pipe or valve malfunction. The experimental data where the actuator fault occurs on the testbed is given in Fig. 4b. In the figure, we can observe that the specific ‘pipe clogging’ fault, reduces the capacity of pump P_1 to send water to tank T_1 between $[2.1, 2.5]$ minutes. The local pressure at the output of pump P_1 is also shown in Fig. 4b. An increase in the pressure is observed, during the fault duration, which would have resulted in the pump shutting down if the fault persisted for longer. The effect of such an actuator fault would be the emptying of subsequent tanks in the system, and thus the cutoff of water supply to consumers.

The actuator fault function is identified using the experimental data and is given by:

$$\xi_i^a(t, u_i; \theta_i^a) = \beta_\nu(t_1, t_2) [\theta_i^a u_i(t)], \quad (14)$$

where $\theta_i^a \in [0, 1]$ corresponds to the percentage of control signal change due to the actuator fault, and $\beta_\nu(t_1, t_2)$ is the fault time profile corresponding to a unit rectangular pulse starting at $t_1 = 2.1min$ and ending at $t_2 = 2.5min$. When $\theta_i^a = 1$ then there is no fault in the actuator system.

5.4 Scenario 4: Sensor faults

Faults in sensors typically appear due to mechanical damage of the sensors, electrical faults at the sensor circuits or power supply, or communication device malfunctions.

In this scenario, we consider a fault that occurs on the electrical connections of the sensor measuring the level of tank T_1 at time $t_1 = 5min$. As part of the experiment, the fault is physically generated by connecting a large resistance in parallel to the sensor electrical connections. Experimental data from the fault are shown in Fig. 4d. The fault function is identified using the data and is given by:

$$\xi_i^s(t) = \beta_\nu(t_1, t_2) [\theta_{i1}^s x_i(t) + \theta_{i2}^s], \quad (15)$$

where $\theta_{i1}^s, \theta_{i2}^s \in \mathbb{R}$ are sensor fault function parameters, and $\beta_\nu(t_1, t_2)$ is the fault time profile corresponding to a unit rectangular pulse starting at $t_1 = 5min$ and ending at the end of the simulation $t_2 = 7min$.

6. WATERSAFE SIMULATOR

To facilitate research in Fault Diagnosis for water systems, we have developed a calibrated simulator corresponding to the experimental setup of the testbed. This will assist in demonstrating results related to the optimization, monitoring, operation, control, and security for water systems. In particular, the use of a realistic simulator can reduce costs and also provide some experience of how to manipulate real-time water processes, thus avoiding the risk of damaging high-cost equipment. This simulation model also permits the computational analysis of process control and monitoring techniques before they are actually applied to the real world.

The WaterSafe Simulator is developed in the MATLAB/Simulink environment and can be used via different interfaces: i) system identification tools, ii) Simulink block diagram, and iii) MATLAB scripts. The simulator allows the user to define an operation mode for the valves, pumps, tanks dynamic in (9), for a water network configuration as the one illustrated in Fig. 1b.

7. DATA AVAILABILITY

All relevant data presented in this article are available online through the permanent GitHub repository <https://github.com/KIOS-Research/WaterSafe-benchmark>. Researchers using the benchmark are invited to experimentally evaluate their solutions through the KIOS Water Systems Testbed. For more information the researchers can contact the KIOS Testbeds team or through the KIOS Testbeds Reservation System at <https://www.kios.ucy.ac.cy>.

8. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper presents a novel benchmark for Fault Diagnosis research, named “WaterSafe”. The benchmark is based on the KIOS Water Systems Testbed, a research infrastructure developed by the KIOS Research and Innovation Center of Excellence at the University of Cyprus, to support activities in the area of smart water systems. WaterSafe is comprised of a MATLAB/Simulink model corresponding to a “tank-in-series” water network configuration of the testbed. A number of faults have been applied to the testbed, in order to create realistic sensor, actuator and process fault models in the benchmark. A detailed mathematical model of the system has been constructed,

and each component has been implemented in Simulink. The model can be used to generate datasets with multiple faults to support research, among others in fault detection, fault isolation and identification, fault accommodation as well as fault-tolerant control. Future work on the WaterSafe benchmark includes the modeling of additional faults on the testbed, including cyber-attacks. Moreover, the model of water quality and specifically the chlorine concentration dynamics will be provided.

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